

A Field-Based Case Study On How Textile is Processed

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Abstract

This field-based case study explains and dives into the chemical and the industrial procedures that are involved in the processing of textile. This was conducted through a visit to a large scale textile processing facility. This will cover the core processes of singeing, desizing, scouring and mercerization, which highlights the chemical mechanisms, operational parameters and industrial applications. The in depth analysis of the mercerization process elucidates the transformation of cellulose fibers under alkaline treatment, its impact on fiber properties, and the challenges that tag along with it. I have tried my level best to keep this case study errorless and fact check everything that I have stated, but there might be a possibility that I may have missed a few things or got something wrong. I apologise for that. I am still a highschool student who is in love with chemistry and I'm open to learning about the concepts that I haven't understood well.

1 Introduction

Processing of textile is an extremely important part of textile manufacturing. Why do I say so? Well, it is essential since all the impurities and contaminants are removed, the wettability of the fiber is improved, the defects and fabric damage are avoided, enhances chemical reactivity which enables consistent and efficient dyeing. The main steps during this procedure are singeing, desizing, scouring and mercerization. I have focused more on the mercerizing part since its more interesting when looked at from a chemistry enthusiast's eyes.

2 Pre-Treatment Processes

2.1 Singeing

Purpose: The main purpose of singeing is to make the surface of the cloth more smooth by getting rid of the rough and protruding fabrics.

Process: As the name suggests, the fabric is singed, i.e. treated with heat by quickly passing it through a flame to remove protruding fibers and fuzz from the fabric surface. The excess fiber that is sticking out is from the yarn. It is composed mostly of cellulose

Figure 1: Fabric after singeing

or cellulose/polyester blend. When it is exposed to flame, the fiber undergoes a reaction which is called an “oxidative pyrolysis”. It’s a combustion reaction where the cellulose will react with the oxygen in air. Since the flame contact time is very brief, only the fizzy part is burnt off and a smooth fabric is obtained without any damage.

Reaction: $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n + O_2 \rightarrow CO_2 + H_2O + \text{Heat}$

Industrial observation: (i) Butane was used as the source of fuel for the flame. (ii) The flame and the time of contact was very precise.

2.2 Desizing

Purpose: Desizing is done in order to remove the starch and the sizing agents that would cause difficulties and lead to a bad yield.

Process: The fabric goes through an enzymatic treatment which helps in the removal of starch, synthetic polymers or other sizing agents used during the weaving process to strengthen the yarn. Chemically, the main goal is to hydrolyse the sizing agent. Enzymes like amylase help catalyze the hydrolysis of starch into soluble sugars. Wetting agents like DTC help increase the water penetration and fabric wetting. Sequestering agents like EDTA bind metal ions that could interact with the enzymes and cause unwanted side reactions. Hydrogen peroxide and Sodium Hydroxide help in the removal of tough residues and adjust the alkalinity of the bath. Acetic acid and Oxalic acid are also added to maintain the pH level of the whole medium. This process is done at 70°C. The cloth is then rotated for 8 hours and then, the obtained cloth is then sent to PTR (Pre Treatment Range) - which is another word for CBR (Continuous Bleaching Range) - for scouring.

Reactions: (i) $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n + nH_2O + \text{enzyme} \rightarrow n(C_6H_{12}O_6)$

(ii) $M^+ + EDTA^{4-} \rightarrow [M-EDTA]^{(n-4)-}$ Here M can be any metal cation like Ca^+ or Fe^{3+}

2.3 Scouring

Purpose: It is done to get rid of natural waxes, pectins, fats, and other hydrophobic impurities from cotton fibers.

Process: Takes place in an alkaline medium. Sodium Hydroxide is treated to the fabric which converts the unwanted fats and waxes into soap and alcohol. Hydrogen peroxide works like an oxidising agent breaking down the other organic impurities, generating hydroxyl radicals. Stabilisers are also added which controls the hydrogen peroxide decomposition. The wetting agent reduces the surface tension which allows the aqueous solution to go through the hydrophobic waxy layers. The whole process takes place at 92°C. The cloth is then sent to a steamer for 14 minutes and another washing is performed.

Reactions: (i) $\text{Fat/waxes (ester)} + NaOH \rightarrow \text{Soap} + \text{Alcohol}$

(ii) $H_2O_2 + OH^- \rightarrow HO_2 + OH\cdot$

3 Mercerization

3.1 Introduction to mercerization

Here is where things get interesting. Mercerization is essentially rearranging the structure of the cellulose of the fabric by applying NaOH to it under controlled tension. This in turn, gives it luster, enhances its tensile strength and improves the dye uptake of the fabric by increasing the number of accessible hydroxyl groups. This process is mainly done to cotton and other fibers made up of cellulose. There are many types of mercerization, each with a minor or major tweak. I'll be talking about two of them. Hot mercerization and cold mercerization. The facility I visited was performing hot mercerisation during my time there. Hence, I will emphasize more on hot mercerization.

3.2 Cold Mercerization

Cold mercerization takes place at around 15–20°C. The fabric is immersed in an NaOH bath of concentration of 33%–35% for about a minute. This causes the fibers to unevenly swell up rapidly making the penetration capacity low. Hence, additional wetting agents are also applied which is not environmentally safe. This is a major reason why it's not favoured. But the low temperature swelling also has its benefits! The fabric's strength is increased and the luster is enhanced. At the end, the fiber is washed and neutralised by Acetic acid.

3.3 Hot Mercerization

Hot mercerization is more industrially favoured, since its easier and way more efficient, has superior properties and wetting agents are not needed. Hot mercerization takes place at around 60–80°C, for a very short amount of time i.e. 10–15 seconds. The facility I visited was mercerizing at 65°C at a uniform tension in order for dimensional stability and a higher dye uptake. Just like cold mercerization, the fabric is dipped in NaOH. But this time the concentration of NaOH is 16%–22%, which is also 260 to 280 GPM. The facility used the unit GPM more than w/w%. The application of tension and correct temperature is extremely crucial for enhancing the luster, maximizing the dye up take, minimizing shrinkage and getting a better feeling fabric. This time the NaOH treatment is done so briefly and at the correctly optimized conditions, the swelling up of the fabric is even, making the feeling of the cloth more smoother than that obtained from cold mercerization. This also means that wetting agents are not needed and the cloth is ready to be taken for dyeing, or as they liked to say, "The batch is now RFD." RFD is an acronym for Ready For Dyeing.

3.4 Reactions Involved

The chemistry involved in mercerization is extremely fascinating. I'll try to explain it to the best of my abilities in 3 steps.

Formation of alkali cellulose: When NaOH is treated to cellulose, the fibers swell up because of the Na⁺ ion penetrating the crystalline region and disturbing the hydrogen bonds. This forms a structure called 'Alkali Cellulose I' or 'Na-cellulose I'

Regeneration to cellulose II: Up to five intermediate Na-cellulose complexes are

formed during this reaction which is not good for the cloth. Washing and alcohol treatment washes the NaOH away and the Na-cellulose I is recrystallised into a different allomorph. This complex is called ‘cellulose II’. It has an anti parallel chain and is irreversible unlike the original parallel chain of cellulose I.

Neutralization: : Acetic acid is used to neutralise the residual NaOH in the aqueous solution. $NaOH + CH_3COOH \rightarrow CH_3COONa + H_2O$

Figure 2: Difference between mercerised and unmercerised cotton

3.5 Mercerization Effectiveness Test

A test called ‘Barium activity test’ is conducted. 1 to 2 grams of mercerized and unmercerized cloth is immersed in 30 ml of 0.25N of $Ba(OH)_2$ for 2 hours. It is then titrated against 0.1N HCl using phenolphthalein as an indicator. Barium activity number (BAN) is then calculated by the formula, $BAN = [(B - M) / (B - U)] \times 100$. An unmercerized sample would give a reading of 100 whereas, a perfect mercerized fabric would give a reading of 130 and above.

3.6 Hot vs Cold Mercerization

Factor	Hot Mercerization	Cold Mercerization
Swelling uniformity	Excellent	Poor
Preprocessing time	Short (20 seconds)	Longer (60 seconds)
Properties	Strong, lustrous, stable	Moderate/limited luster and strength
Wetting agents	Not needed	May be required
Popularity	Widely used	Uncommon/very niche

4 Conclusion

From singeing off the stray fuzz to modifying cellulose on a molecular basis, textile processing is a unique combination of chemistry and engineering. Each stage of textile processing – singeing, desizing, scouring, and eventually mercerizing which is a logical progression from stage to stage, altering the fabric properties and eliminating non-cellulosic impurities, making cellulose more reactive, and developing the aesthetic and performance characteristics of the final fabric. Cold mercerization is cost effective in obtaining luster and tensile gain. However, from an industry perspective, hot mercerization has an unbeatable advantage over cold mercerization due to its efficiency in providing uniform swelling, along with superior end results without wetting agents. Seeing the processing of

textiles up close made me realize, in a way that I never considered before, how much precision, control, and chemical understanding it takes to develop something as "everyday" as cotton clothes! It isn't just dunking a fabric in alkali, it is a process of transformation that involves choreography of cellulose itself which has to have temperature, tension, and time dancing to the same rhythm to transform a simple fiber into something that can later shine, quite literally, on the loom, in the dye bath, and lastly in someone's closet.

Sources and References

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